

Banks Consolidation and Real Estate Finance in Nigeria

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Abstract

The study evaluates the performance of commercial banks in real estate financing before (2000-2004) and after (2005 – 2009) the consolidation exercise of banks in Nigeria with a view to establishing its impact on real estate development. A total number of 255 questionnaire were administered on members of the Real Estate Developers Association of Nigeria while 157 of the questionnaire were retrieved for analysis representing 61.56% response rate. Also, data were obtained from 17 banks out of 19 consolidated banks in Nigeria representing 89.47% response rate. The remaining number of banks did not divulge information concerning their banks activities. The data collected were analyzed using the Mean Score Method and index numbers, t – test and Correlation Coefficient. Mean score and index numbers were used to measure banks' performance while T-test and Correlation analysis were employed to establish whether there is difference between loan and advances of banks during the pre and post consolidation era, and the nature and degree of relationship of real estate financing and the banks' capital base and the banks' deposits. The result showed that the commercial banks' performance in real estate financing only improved minimally after Banks' Consolidation compared to the pre – consolidation era where no fund was allocated. The study recommends that the Federal Government should come up with policies to increase the percentage of commercial banks' loans and advances to real estate sector.

Keywords: Consolidation, Capital base, Bank deposit, Real estate, Finance.

Introduction

Investment in Real estate accounts for a substantial portion of the worlds' wealth. Hence the sector is one of the most profitable ventures of every economy and one of the indices of measuring economic growth of a society (Omeru, 2011). In the developed economies, real estate investment has been properly integrated into the finance sector, playing a crucial role in their national economy (Atilola and Nubi, 2010). In Nigeria, the contribution of real estate sector to the National Gross Domestic Product (GDP) has been on the rise since 2000, with estimation of 1.86%, 2.72%, and 3.27% for year 2000, 2004 and 2009 respectively (CBN, 2010). Also according to Enhancing Financial Innovation and Access Report (2010), the average growth rate in the sector between 2000 and 2005 was 10.7%. However, the sector depends largely on banks for its effectiveness as a result of the huge capital to drive it (Omeru, 2011). Therefore, the intermediation role of banks (both commercial and mortgage) in channeling funds to the sector is of paramount importance.

The commercial banks are the principal source of short-term credit of most business lending and a major source of real estate finance in the United States and Nigeria in particular (Sherman, 1987). The banks are supposed to perform three distinct functions in real estate financing

which include; provision of primary source for construction and interim (short-term) financing; a major source of long - term lending; and through nationwide subsidiaries, they conduct an extensive business in originating trading and services mortgages (Sherman, 1987). Despite these functions, the commercial banks have witnessed a lot of crisis over the years in the country. The crises started with the inability of the banks to meet up with its financial obligation to its stakeholders (Adegbaju and Olokoyo, 2008). This can be particularly damaging because they entail a major disruption in economic activity. In most cases, the banks and their customers engage in massive credit recalls and withdrawals which sometimes necessitate Central Bank liquidity support to the affected banks (Adegbaju and Olokoyo, 2008). This crisis necessitated the banking sector reforms in 2004 where commercial banks were left with the option of carrying out consolidation exercise.

However, before the landmark consolidation exercise of banks, Nigeria Commercial Banks operated below economic expectation; the growth in Commercial Banks' credit (made up of loans and advances) failed to consistently track the growth rates of the economy (Meristem Securities Limited, 2008). The implication was that banks failed to provide sufficient loan for financing various sectors including the real estate thus

making it difficult to propel the much needed economic growth. Since finance is the bedrock for real estate development there is the need to assess any change in policies which might have direct or indirect influences on flow of funds into the real estate sector (Sherman, 1987; Atilola and Nubi, 2010). Banks being the major source of funds for real estate development, the need therefore arose to appraise the performance of commercial banks in real estate financing before and after banks consolidation exercise.

Banks Consolidation and Real Estate financing

The consolidation of banks is the major policy instrument adopted in correcting deficiency in the financial sector (Dogarawa, 2011). The Nigeria banking sector reform of 2004 was to strengthen the banking industry, so that big banks that have greater capacity to absorb various kinds of adverse economic conditions would emerge (Okagbue and Aluko, 2005). To strengthen the banking industry and improve availability of credit to the various sector, Banks were required to raise their capital base from about N2 billion to N25 billion minimum before the end of 2005. In order to meet this requirement, most of the banks opted for consolidation by way of merger and acquisition, with those who could not raise fund from the capital market or agree mergers, losing their licenses (Emeka, 2009). In the process of meeting the new capital requirements, banks raised the equivalent of about N359 billion from the domestic capital market and attracted about N12.74 billion of foreign investment into the Nigerian banking sector (Fadare, 2010).

The consolidation exercise led to acceleration of growth in private sector credit extension from N1.2 trillion in 2003 to N4.9 trillion in 2007, with credit to the private sector increasing from 14% of GDP in 2003 to 24% of GDP in 2007 (Emeka et al 2008). According to Olubayo et al (2011), the consolidation exercise brought about significant economic benefits through improved bank operational efficiency and effectiveness in order to guarantee a more effective mobilization and efficient allocation of resources among various economic units. In relation to bank financing (credit availability), a number of factors determine the volume of loans that banks gives, capital base and deposits are considered the most important as articulated by Kahn (1991), Jackson et al. (1999), Hensa (2000) and Deutsche Bundes Bank (2005).

Bank consolidation is proxy by capital base and bank deposits as in the work of Dogarawa (2011). Bank capital is shareholders' funds that is attributed to the

proprietors (Oluyinka, 2004). These funds are made up of two components - primary and supplementary. Primary capital represents resources which can be used to meet current losses while leaving the bank to continue operating on an ongoing concern basis (Nwankwo, 2004). The second category is the supplementary capital. These include all those instruments which, while not possessing the full qualities of primary capital, are nonetheless available to support losses on an ongoing concern basis (Nwankwo, 2004). In order to arrive at the operating capital fund, primary and supplementary funds are aggregated together from which other liabilities are deducted, the balance gives operating capital (Nwankwo, 2004).

Bank recapitalization is the upgrading of banks' capital base (Oluyinka, 2004). Increasing capital base of banks has become the hallmark response policy of the Nigerian monetary authorities (Oboh, 2005). Attaining capitalization requirements may be achieved through consolidation of existing banks or raising additional funds through the capital market (Adegbaaju and lokoyo, 2008). Strong capital base is a basic indication of solvency, a bank with a strong capital base has the ability to absorb losses arising from non-performing liabilities as sudden stops in capital flows represent a major vulnerability to financial stability (Herald 2004). According to Afrinvest West Africa report (2008), in 2007 alone, up to 15 of the surviving banks in Nigeria made arrangements to raise new money, with average deal sizes within the US\$250m to US\$300m range, and a number of banks doing deals in the US\$750m to US\$1bn range.

Sangosanya as cited in Atilola and Nubi (2010) noted that the low bank capitalization coupled with the peculiar features of real estate such as low yield and longer repayment periods make it difficult for the banks to meet up with demand for real estate finance. An estimated N359 billion was raised by banking sector from private placements and public offer, while the consolidation exercise of the banking sector attracted foreign investment inflow to the sector to the tune of US \$86 million, (about N12.4 billion) and another £162,000 (about N340 million) (Ningi and Dutse, 2008).

Termos (2005), in a study on banking structure and the effect of monetary policy on bank lending, found that capital base of the bank is most crucial for real estate lending. The effect of capitalization in Nigeria banks has led to strengthen operational capacity of banks in funding real estate development (Atilola and Nubi, 2010). For example, in 2005, 11 banks were to raise

₦100 billion bonds to finance the purchase of Federal Government houses in Abuja (The Punch, 2005). Also, the Lagos state Government in 2007 launched “The Lagos Mortgage Scheme” aimed at putting together the sum of ₦40 billion by a consortium of 5 banks for Lagosians to access mortgage loan, while a consortium of banks also funded the development of Muritala Mohammed International Airport 2 with about ₦12 billion (Atilola and Nubi, 2010). While ₦700 billion was advanced to real estate investors and speculators, credit to the private sector increased from 14% of GDP in 2003 to 24% of GDP in 2007, out of which real estate and construction constitute 6% (Emeka et al. 2008; Oni, 2012). Real estate exposure for banks was only 10% of total loan portfolios of the private sector (Merrill Lynch Research Report, 2007). Commercial banks in Nigeria also invested directly by floating a subsidiary property company, while others invested indirectly in real estate development.

While consolidation has resulted in mega banks in Nigeria with sound capital base and relative stability in service delivery, it is however, argued that for the banks, it has not translated into a deepening of the quality of financial intermediation (Dogarawa, 2011). While it can be argued that recapitalization has helped to build and foster a competitive and a more stable banking environment, it is debatable if the structure of their portfolio investments has the capacity to support the desired economic development aspiration of the proponents of banking consolidation (Balogun, 2007). One reason put forward as to why consolidated banks are less likely to lend to some businesses particularly those in need of working capital financing is that large banks tend to rely on formal, formulaic methods of determining whether to lend or not and the amount to give (Berger and Udell, 2002; Craig and Hardee, 2004; Berger, Rosen and Udell, 2007).

Daniel and Frederico (2008) sought to identify the effects of bank concentration on lending in Brazil, based on the hypothesis that consolidation of the banking sector reduces the number of loans granted. The results obtained corroborated the hypothesis that the process of consolidation in the Brazilian banking sector had an adverse effect on lending.

However, Chinedu and Chinwe (2011) noted that increase in capital base and reserve which had significant positive effects on credit to the production size of the population of the REDAN members. The formula is given as:

sector before consolidation, became insignificant, and indeed exhibited an inverse relationship after consolidation. Fadare (2010) also noted that, some of the negative impacts of the consolidation exercise on the Nigerian economy included reduced lending to the real estate sector; decreased economic activities and massive job losses in most sectors of the economy; declining capital inflows in the economy; and limited foreign trade finances for banks with credit lines drying up for some banks.

Furthermore, Balogun (2007) showed that, there is significant and positive correlation between banking sector total assets, capital and reserves and total credit as well as production credit granted by the banks. Therefore increased capital base should lead to increased supply and improved access to credit. That is, increase in capital base should lead to increase in the real estate sector financing (Balogun, 2007).

Interestingly in Nigeria, studies have centered on Banks' Consolidation and its effect on lending to various sectors of the economy with little attention given to the real estate sector (Balogun, 2007; Fadare, 2010; Dogarawa, 2011; Chinedu and Chinwe, 2011). The only known studies on the effect of consolidation of banks on the real estate sector was that of Atilola and Nubi (2010); Omeru (2011) and Oni (2012). These studies noted that Banks Consolidation impacted negatively on real estate transaction but the studies did not back up the findings with empirical evidence. It is in this regard that this research is undertaken to fill the gap that exist.

Research Methodology

The data for the study was collected from the headquarters of each of the commercial banks in Nigeria and the Real Estate Developers Association of Nigeria (REDAN) from six geo – political zones of Nigeria. The sample frame for REDAN in the six geo – political zones are one thousand, one hundred and sixty four (1164) as detailed in the (2013) REDAN Directory while that of the commercial banks are 19 as given by the Central Bank after consolidation of banks. The sample size for the banks comprises the whole of the 19 consolidated banks in Nigeria. The sample size is in conformity with Israel (2003), who suggested the use of census method for small sample frame that is less than 200. Kothari (2004) formula was used to determine the sample

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot p \cdot q \cdot N}{e^2 (N-1) + Z^2 \cdot p \cdot q} \text{ ----- (i)}$$

Where, n = sample size

z = value of standard deviation at a confidence level taken from table of normal curve at variants (z) for 95% confidence, which is 1.96

p = sample proportion (q=1-p) which in this study is taken as 9% (0.09)

N = size of the population from sample frame of 1,163 members

e = error margin estimated at 5% (0.05)

The estimated sample size, using the formula, was 255. Questionnaire were administered on the 255 REDAN members out of which 157 were retrieved representing 61.56% response rate (Table 1). Also, questionnaire were administered on 19 commercial banks out of which data was collected from 17 commercial banks representing 89.47% response rate. The remaining banks did not divulge information on their banking activities.

The tools for data analysis involve simple descriptive statistics (Frequency Distribution Table, index number and Mean Score), t – test and correlation analysis. Descriptive statistics such as Mean Score, Frequency Distribution Table and Index Numbers were used to measure banks’ performance, while t-test and Correlation analysis (inferential statistics) were employed to establish whether there is difference between loans and advances of banks before and after consolidation era; and the nature and degree of relationship between real estate financing and the banks’ capital base and banks’ deposits.

Table 1: Questionnaire Administration.

S/No	ZONE	Number of REDAN members	Sample Size and Number of administered	Number of Questionnaire Returned	of (%) Returned
1	North Central	419	91	77	84.6
2	North East	31	8	6	75.0
3	North West	43	10	7	70.0
4	South East	48	10	6	60.0
5	South West	469	103	52	51.0
6	South South	154	33	9	27.3
TOTAL		1164	255	157	61.56

Analysis and Discussion of Results

Sectoral capital allocation of commercial banks' loans and advances

Table 2: Sectoral capital allocation of commercial banks' loans and advances before and after consolidation

Activities	Pre-consolidation						Post-consolidation					
	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	Mean	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	Mean
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%
Agriculture	8.05	7.01	6.27	5.13	4.46	6.2	2.46	1.96	3.11	1.88	1.28	2.1
Manufacturing	27.80	26.00	24.46	24.32	21.86	24.9	17.81	17.66	10.13	10.69	11.29	13.5
Mining and Quarrying	6.35	8.81	7.35	7.93	8.63	7.8	8.73	9.96	10.19	10.07	11.31	10.1
Real Estate	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.00	5.9	6.2	6.2	8.3	6.7
Import and Export	4.98	4.34	2.80	2.85	2.06	3.4	1.34	2.09	1.38	2.95	12.01	4.0
Public Utilities	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.53	0.77	0.3
Transport and Communication	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	14.62	10.90	5.1
Credit to Financial Institution	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.52	9.26	3.2
Government	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	33.63	0.55	6.8
Miscellaneous	52.80	53.81	59.10	59.76	63.00	57.7	69.66	68.33	75.18	36.52	33.22	56.6

Table 2 presents the capital allocation of commercial banks loans and advances to various sectors of the economy including the real estate sector from year 2000 to 2009. Year 2000 to 2009 was taken to have equal number of years before and after the banks consolidation. Miscellaneous, Manufacturing, Mining and Quarrying, Agriculture and Imports and Exports sectors received a mean of 57.7%, 24.9%, 7.8%, 6.2%, and 3.4% respectively for loans and advances before the bank consolidation exercise. At the same time, Real Estate, Public Utilities, Transport and Communication, Financial Institutions and Government received 0% allocation each before consolidation.

In the post-consolidation period, Real Estate, Financial Institutions, Public Utilities, Government and Transport and Communication received percentage means of 6.7%, 5.1%, 6.8%, 3.2%, 2.6%, 0.3% of loan and advances respectively, while miscellaneous, manufacturing, mining and quarrying, agriculture and imports and exports sectors received 56.6%, 13.5%, 10.1%, 2.1% and 4.0% respectively. The result shows that the less productive sectors of the economy are favoured in the sectoral allocation of credit and this finding is in tandem with the findings of Ebong (n.d) that the less productive sectors are more favoured in sectoral loan allocation.

Contribution of various sectors into national Gross Domestic Product

Table 3: Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of various economic activities

Activities	Pre-consolidation						Post-consolidation					
	2000 %	2001 %	2002 %	2003 %	2004 %	Mean %	2005 %	2006 %	2007 %	2008 %	2009 %	Mean %
Agriculture	35.83	34.95	39.52	32.60	34.21	34.8	32.76	41.72	42.01	42.13	41.84	40.1
Manufacturing	4.24	7.77	6.52	4.70	3.07	5.3	2.85	3.91	4.03	4.14	4.18	3.8
Mining and Quarrying	32.75	36.37	34.69	41.60	37.33	36.3	38.99	22.13	19.90	17.66	16.38	23.1
Real Estate	3.39	3.83	4.02	4.30	5.36	4.2	6.15	6.29	6.39	6.50	6.60	6.4
Public Utilities	0.44	0.25	0.28	0.24	0.23	0.3	0.20	3.54	3.49	3.42	3.31	2.8
Transport & Communication	12.11	2.65	2.50	2.49	3.40	4.6	2.93	4.44	4.99	5.63	6.39	4.9
Credit to Financial Institution	5.21	0.78	1.02	0.82	0.91	1.8	0.90	3.90	3.85	3.81	3.71	3.2
Government	1.16	1.46	1.35	1.17	1.14	1.3	1.02	0.94	0.94	0.93	0.93	1.0
Miscellaneous	0.82	0.77	0.86	0.80	0.88	0.8	0.87	0.77	0.80	0.80	0.84	0.8

Table 3 shows the contribution of the various sector to the GDP of the economy. Before the consolidation exercise, Agriculture and Mining and Quarrying contributed more to the National Gross Domestic Product with mean percentage of 34.8 and 36.3 respectively. Sectors like Real Estate, Manufacturing, Transport and Communication, Credit to Financial Institutions, Government, Miscellaneous and Public Utilities contributed mean percentages of 4.2, 5.3, 4.6, 1.8, 1.3, 0.8 and 0.3 respectively. However, after the consolidation exercise, Real Estate, Agriculture, Transport and Communication, Financial Institutions and Public Utilities increased to 6.4%, 40.1%, 4.9%, 3.2%, and 2.8% while Manufacturing and Mining and Quarrying fell to 3.8% and 23.1%.

Comparison of Sectors' contribution to National GDP and Sectoral allocation of loan and advances.

The contributions of each sector to the national economy with the loans and advances allocated by commercial banks to each sector were compared. The result is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Various Sectors' Percentage mean Contribution to GDP and percentage means of Loans and Advances

Activity	Pre-consolidation			Post-consolidation		
	% Contribution to GDP	Mean to & Advances	Loan	% Contribution to GDP	Mean to & Advances	Loan
Agriculture	34.8	6.2		40.1	2.1	
Manufacturing	5.3	24.9		3.8	13.5	
Mining & Quarrying	36.6	7.8		23.0	10.1	
Real Estate	4.2	0.0		6.4	6.7	
Public Utilities	0.3	0.0		2.8	0.3	
Trans. & Comm.	4.6	0.0		4.9	5.1	
Financial Institutions	1.8	0.00		3.2	3.2	
Government	1.3	0.00		0.9	6.8	
Miscellaneous	0.8	57.7		0.8	56.6	

Table 4 shows the contribution of various sectors to the gross domestic product and the loans and advances allocated to each sector. Before the banks consolidation exercise, Agriculture, Mining and Quarrying sectors contributed 34.8%, and 36.6% to the National Gross Domestic Product and received 6.2% and 7.8% of the total loans and advances respectively. Manufacturing sector which contributed only 5.3% was allocated 24.9% of the total loans and advances. Real Estate, Transport and Communication, Financial Institutions and Government sectors contributed 4.2%, 4.6%, 1.8%, 1.3% to the National Gross Domestic Product and each received 0% allocation of loans and advances. Miscellaneous sector was allocated 57.7% of the total loans and advances with only 0.8% contribution to the National Gross Domestic Product.

After the bank consolidation exercise, Real Estate sector contributed 6.4% to GDP but received 6.7% of loan and

advances, whereas, Miscellaneous and Manufacturing sectors which contributed only 0.8 % and 3.8% respectively were allocated 56.6% and 13.5% of loan and advances respectively. Agriculture contributed 40.1% to the national GDP, and only 2.1% of banks credit exposure (loan and advances) was given to the sector while Miscellaneous, Mining and Quarrying and Manufacturing sectors which contributed 0.8%, 23% and 3.8 only, 56.6%, 10.1% and 13.5% was given as loan and advances respectively. Transport and Communication contributed 4.9% but only received 5.1% of loans and advances.

To show that the observed difference in the contribution of the sector to GDP, loan and advances made by banks to the various sector before and after the consolidation exercise (as shown in table 4) were not due to chances occurrence, Paired Samples T – Test was carried out. The result is shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Paired Samples T-Test of Various Sectors’ Percentage means of GDP and percentage means of Loans and Advances.

		Paired Differences			95% Interval Difference Upper	Confidence of the Lower	t	Df	Sig. (2- tailed)
		Mean	Std. Devi.	Std. Error Mean					
Pair 1	GDP pre – GDP post	0.475	5.69	2.012	-4.284	5.234	0.236	7	0.820
Pair 2	L&A pre - L&A post	-1.113	6.21	2.194	-6.301	4.076	-0.507	7	0.628

The result in Table 5 revealed that the percentage means of GDP Pre and Post consolidation and the Loans and Advances Pre and Post consolidation has their confidence intervals entirely below 0.00, which implies that the sectors contribution to GDP and the Loan and Advances to the sectors are not significant at 5 ($p \leq 0.05$). This is not unexpected as sectors which contributed so much to the GDP were seen receiving little or no allocations. This finding is in conformity with the findings of Emeka et al (2008) that there is significant mismatch between where credit is supplied (by sector) and the main contributors to gross domestic product in Nigeria.

Performance of Nigerian Commercial Banks in Real Estate financing.

Table 6: Performance of Nigerian commercial banks in real estate financing

Period	Year	Numbers of Properties Developed	of Numbers Developed with secured from commercial banks	Properties with capital secured from commercial banks	Percentage
Pre-consolidation	2000	3041	1407		46.3
	2001	3215	861		26.8
	2002	2668	929		34.8
	2003	1921	1027		53.5
	2004	2634	728		27.6
	Mean		2696	999	
Post-consolidation	2005	1072	891		83.1
	2006	2751	953		34.6
	2007	3215	1214		37.8
	2008	1183	838		70.8
	2009	3293	1915		58.1
	Mean		2303	1162	

Table 6 shows the mean number of property developed before the consolidation exercise to be 2696, out of which 999 were developed with capital secured from commercial banks. After banks consolidation exercise, the mean number of properties developed was 2303, out of which 1162 was developed with capital secured from commercial banks representing 50.5%. This translates to an increase of 13.4% in the number of properties developed with fund secured from commercial banks after consolidation. The mean increment of 13.4% in the number of properties developed with capital secured from commercial bank after consolidation exercise shows that bank consolidation though impacted positively on real estate financing; the impact is still very minimal since the sector depends much on banks' finance to survive. Number of properties developed with fund secured from commercial banks was further subjected to index number analysis to establish the annual performance of banks in real estate financing before and after the consolidation exercise.

Table 7: Index analysis of Banks' performance

Period	Year	Numbers of Properties Developed with capital secured from Commercial banks	Cumulative	Index	Percentage
Pre-Consolidation	2000	1407	1407	1.00	46.3
	2001	861	2268	1.61	26.8
	2002	929	3197	2.27	34.8
	2003	1027	4224	3.00	53.5
	2004	728	4952	3.52	27.6
Post-Consolidation	2005	891	891	1.00	83.1
	2006	953	1844	2.07	34.6
	2007	1214	3058	3.43	37.8
	2008	838	3896	4.37	70.8
	2009	1915	5811	6.52	58.1

Table 7 shows the index analysis of Banks performance over the years during the pre and post consolidation period. The result however, revealed that the index numbers increased from 1 in 2000 to 3.52 in 2004. After

banks consolidation exercise (2005 -2009), the index number rose from 1 in 2005 to 6.52 in 2009.

Relationship between Real Estate financing, Capital Base of the Bank and Banks' Deposits

Number of properties developed with fund sourced from commercial banks was used to represent real estate financed by commercial banks, since both the banks and the developers would not divulge information about the actual funds granted or obtained. The data collected is presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Numbers of properties developed with fund from commercial banks, Capital base of the banks and Banks' deposits.

Year	Number of Properties developed with capital secured from commercial banks	Capital base ₦m	Bank deposit ₦m
2000	1407	20,105	378,411
2001	861	73,423	744,014
2002	929	119,166	866,213
2003	1027	156,905	1,124,541
2004	728	216,948	1,313,027
2005	891	378,441	1,937,650
2006	953	709,351	4,185,079
2007	1214	1,039,840	5,853,429
2008	838	1,987,343	6,575,591
2009	1915	1,796,484	6,092,221

Banks deposits and Capital base of banks exhibits increment on annual basis from ₦378,411 million in year 2000 to ₦6.092221 trillion in 2009 and ₦20.105 billion in 2000 to ₦1.796484 trillion in 2009 respectively, while number of properties developed with fund from commercial banks fluctuates (Table 8). In year 2000, the number of properties developed were 1407 and in 2002 the number dropped to 929 properties. In 2008, properties developed dropped to 838 after it picked up in 2005, 2006 and 2007 respectively.

Table 9: Correlations between property developed, capital base and bank deposits

		PPTYDEV	BCAPBASE	BDEPOSIT
PPTYDEV	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	1		
BCAPBASE	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	0.391	1	
BDEPOSIT	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	0.352	0.952**	1
		0.318	0.000	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation matrix shown in Table 9 indicated the level of relationship between properties developed, Capital base and Bank deposit. The correlation coefficient between property developed and capital base is 0.391 ($P > 0.05$) so also, the correlation coefficient between property developed and bank deposit is 0.352, ($P > 0.05$). The results however, show the correlation coefficient to be greater than zero indicating a weak linear relationship between the variables (properties developed, Capital base and Bank deposit). The result although not significant are however, not contrary to expectation in an economy where things are not working as expected. For instance, the Central Bank of Nigeria consolidation policy was aimed at increasing Banks Capital which would lead to increase in the credit size to all sectors of the economy including the real estate sector. This however, turned out not to be true.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Commercial banks' performance in real estate financing improved minimally after banks consolidation compared to pre consolidation era. However, this is not as a result of the increase in capital base of banks and banks' deposits, because

there is no significant relationship between real estate financing by commercial banks and both the capital base of the banks and banks' deposits.

Although the 2004 bank consolidation exercise increased capital base of banks and banks deposits, however, it has not translated into increased financing (lending) to real estate sector. Therefore bank consolidation in Nigeria has no positive impact on the size of finance available to real estate development.

Taking into consideration the peculiarities of real estate sector and its contribution to the economy, the Federal Government should come up with more realistic and realizable policies to increase the percentage of banks' loans and advances to real estate sector and reducing cost of capital. This will no doubt enhance accessibility of real estate sector to finance.

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